

Microbial Pigments: Insights into Diversity, Biosynthesis, and Multifaceted Applications

Naorem Geetanjali Devi 1 , Sobiya R A 1 , Lavanya P 1 and Angayarkanni T 1, *

1. Department of Biochemistry, Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Avinashilingam Institute for Home Science and Higher Education for Women, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

*** Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, Biotechnology and Bioinformatics, Avinashilingam Institute for Home Science and Higher Education for Women, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.**

Email: angayrakann_bc@avinuty.ac.in

Abstract

Naturally derived colorants from microorganisms have attracted significant interest as sustainable and environmentally conscious substitutes for Artificial and chemicals colorants. These biologically active substances are synthesized by diverse groups of microbes, including bacteria, fungi, yeasts, and algae, and are known not only for their vivid hues but also for their strong antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities. With advances in green extraction technologies and microbial fermentation, pigments are now increasingly being integrated into various sectors, including textiles, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, aquaculture, and nanotechnology. This manuscript provides a comprehensive overview of microbial pigment diversity, biosynthetic sources, and their broad-spectrum industrial and environmental applications, culminating in a discussion on their potential to support sustainable development.

Keywords: Bio pigments; Sustainable dyes; Natural colorants; Secondary metabolites; Environmental sustainability

1. Introduction

Colors are one of the most noticeable and appealing features of any product, playing a vital role in consumer attraction across Sectors including nutrition, beauty, apparel, and healthcare. Although synthetic dyes have long been favoured for their vibrant hues, stability, and cost-effectiveness, increasing awareness of their potential toxicity and environmental hazards has led to growing interest in natural alternatives.[1] Among natural colors sources, pigment-producing microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and microalgae have shown immense potential. These microbial pigments are not only biodegradable and eco-friendly, but they also offer added benefits due to their bioactive properties. They are known for their broad biological activities, including fighting infections, preventing oxidative stress, reducing inflammation, and exhibiting anticancer effects, making them valuable not just as colorants but also for their therapeutic applications.[2][3]

Despite these advantages, natural pigments face several limitations, including higher production costs, lower colors intensity, and reduced stability compared to synthetic dyes. As a result, synthetic pigments continue to dominate commercial markets, particularly because they can be mass-produced affordably and in a wide range of colors. Nevertheless, growing regulatory concerns and safety guidelines from global organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO), U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) are pushing industries toward safer, natural alternatives.[1] The exploration of Microbe-derived pigment sources remains relatively underdeveloped in many regions, particularly in India, indicating a significant need for more focused research in this area. With advancements in microbial technology, fermentation processes, and strain

improvement, it is becoming increasingly possible to enhance the yield, stability, and bioactivity of microbial pigments for commercial use. [4] This review explores the various microbial sources of natural pigments and their potential applications, particularly in the pharmaceutical field. It highlights their biological and therapeutic properties, and discusses key strategies to improve their production and functionality. Emphasis is placed on overcoming current limitations to enable large-scale, sustainable use of microbial pigments across multiple industries

2. Natural Pigments

Natural pigments are gaining increasing attention due to their aesthetic appeal, health-promoting benefits, and broad applicability across various industries. Concerns over the risks posed by artificial colorants are pushing the industry to adopt more sustainable and non-toxic pigment options. Eco-sourced pigments are particularly valued for their non-toxic, biodegradable, and non-carcinogenic properties, making them an attractive replacement for synthetic dyes in food, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, textiles, and other commercial sectors.[5]

The two primary biological sources of natural pigments are plants and microorganisms. While plant-derived pigments have traditionally dominated the market, microbial pigments are now emerging as a superior alternative. Microorganisms, such as bacteria, fungi, and algae, can produce pigments more rapidly and efficiently in controlled environments. Unlike plants, microbial growth and pigment production are not significantly influenced by seasonal or climatic variations, allowing for year-round production using simple and inexpensive culture media.[6][7] Microbial pigments offer a sustainable solution for industrial-scale production. They can be cultivated using both solid-state and submerged fermentation techniques, utilizing cost-effective substrates, including organic industrial waste or food by-products. This approach not only promotes waste valorisation but also aligns with circular

economy principles.[8]Common microbial pigments include carotenoids, melanin, violacein, flavins, quinones, monascins, and others, many of which exhibit potent physiological benefits including protection against oxidation, microbial infection, inflammatory conditions, anticancer, immunosuppressive, and ant proliferative effects[9]. These multifunctional properties have made microbial pigments particularly appealing for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications.[10]

Despite these benefits, there are still challenges associated with natural pigments. Compared to synthetic dyes, natural pigments tend to have lower stability, limited color range, and reduced resistance to environmental factors such as heat, light, and pH variations.[11] Furthermore, regulatory approval processes for new natural colorants can be time-consuming and restrictive, particularly when the pigments are intended for use in food or medical products.[12]

There are two main strategies for enhancing the commercial viability of microbial pigment production:

1. Discovery of new pigment-producing strains from diverse and extreme environments (e.g., soil, marine ecosystems, hot springs).
2. Strain improvement and process optimization using genetic engineering, metabolic pathway modification, and advanced fermentation techniques to increase yield and pigment quality from known microbial strains.

To achieve high and consistent pigment production, it is essential to optimize key environmental and nutritional parameters, including temperature, pH, aeration, agitation speed, light exposure, and carbon/nitrogen sources. Advances in genetic manipulation and synthetic biology are being utilized to reprogram microbial metabolism for improved pigment

production efficiency and higher output.[13][14] In addition, food waste and agricultural residues have shown promise as low-cost substrates for microbial pigment production. Several studies have reported the successful use of these waste materials to cultivate pigment-producing microbes, adding both economic and environmental value to the process. Natural pigments are particularly those derived from microorganisms that's offer a promising, sustainable alternative to synthetic dyes. Their multifunctional properties and eco-friendly nature make them highly relevant to current industrial needs. Continued research into strain discovery, fermentation optimization, and regulatory support will be essential to fully realize the commercial potential of microbial pigments across sectors.[15]

Table1. List of Pigment Producing Microorganisms (Konuray and Erginkaya 2015)

Name of the strain	Colour Produced	Properties	Reference
<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	Yellow	Algicidal	[13]
<i>Neurospora sp</i>	Orange-red	Oncostatic	[14]
<i>Achromobacter</i>	Pink, orange, Red	Cancer-inhibitory, Antiparasitic	[15]
<i>H. alexandrinus</i>	Red	Antiprotozoal	[16]
<i>Bacillus sp.</i>	Pink, orange, yellow	Bactericidal	[17]
<i>Brevibacterium sp.</i>	Orange	Antioxidant	[18]
<i>Clavibacter michiganensis</i>	Pink, yellow	Antitumor	[19]
<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i>	Brown,	Bactericide	[20]

	Yellow–green,		
<i>Arthrobacter</i>	Yellow	Cytotoxic	[21]
<i>C. infirmominiatum</i>	Red	Antibacterial	[22]
<i>R. maris</i>	Deep red	Antibiotic	[22]
<i>Streptomyces</i> sp.	Blue, red, yellow	Antibiotic	[22]
<i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	Red, Orange	Antibacterial	[22]
<i>A. glaucus</i>	Dark red	Anticancer	[22]
<i>B. trispora</i>	Cream	Tambjamines (BE-18591, Antibiotic)	[23]
<i>H. catenarium</i>	Red	UV-shielding	[23]
<i>H. gramineum</i>	Red	UV Protection	[24]
<i>H. cynodontis</i>	Bronze color	Antibiotic	[23]
<i>H. avenae</i>	Bronze color	Antibiotic	[23]
<i>M. purpureus</i>	Red, orange, yellow	Antiproliferative	[25]
<i>P. cyclopium</i>	Orange	Inhibits cell growth	[26]
<i>P. nalgiovense</i>	Red	Inhibits cell growth	[27]
<i>Cryptococcus</i> sp.	Red	Inhibits algae	[23]
<i>P. rhodozyma</i>	Orange	Antiprotozoal	[28]
<i>Rhodotorula</i> sp.	Orange/red, Yellow	Anti-tumor	[29]
<i>Y. lipolytica</i>	Brown	Antiprotozoal	[30]
<i>D. salina</i>	Red, Orange	Antiprotozoal	[31]
<i>S. roseus</i>	Reddish-pink	Anticancer; Algicidal	[32]

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Table2. Low cost media used in pigment production

Microorganisms	Pigment	Media used	References
<i>R. gracilis</i> MTCC 884	β -Carotene	Potato wastewater	[33]
<i>R. toruloides</i> ATCC204091	Total Carotenoids	Vegetable Waste	[34]
<i>R. glutinis</i> Y1	Total Carotenoids	Vegetable Waste	[34]
<i>R. rubra</i> GED8	Total Carotenoids	Whey	[35]
<i>R. glutinis</i>	Total Carotenoids	Whey	[36]
<i>R. faecalis</i> PA2	Lycopene	Agro waste	[37]
<i>R. sphaeroides</i> O.U.001	Total Carotenoids	Wastewater	[38]
<i>R. mucilaginosa</i>	β -Carotene, Torularhodin, torulene	Wastewater	[39]
<i>R. toruloides</i>	Total Carotenoids	Wheat straw hydrolysates	[40]
<i>L. starkeyi</i>	Total Carotenoids	Wheat straw hydrolysates	[40]
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	β -Carotene	Lignocellulosic biomass	[41]
<i>S. roseus</i>	Total Carotenoids	Coffee waste	[42]
<i>P. fermentans</i>	Total Carotenoids	Rice water	[43]
<i>H. pluvialis</i>	Astaxanthin	Horticultural waste	[44]

<i>X.dendrorhous</i>	Astaxanthin	Kitchen scraps	[45]
<i>Enterobactersp.PWN1</i>	Prodigoin	Casein acid hydrolysate	[46]
<i>A.carbonarius</i>	Melanin	Fruit and vegetable waste	[47]
<i>C.violaceumUTM5</i>	Violacein	Fruit waste	[48]

3. Types of Microbial Pigments

3.1. Carotenoids: Microbial Sources, Properties, and Applications

Carotenoids represent a major class of naturally occurring pigments commonly found in both plants and various microorganisms. These compounds are recognized for their bright yellow, orange, and red hues, are classified as isoprenoid polyenes due to their long chains of conjugated double bonds. Carotenoids are fat-soluble and structurally diverse, typically consisting of 35–40 carbon atoms arranged in a polyene chain that may form cyclic or acyclic structures.[49] While plants are well-known producers of carotenoids, A wide variety of microorganisms including bacteria, yeasts, molds, viruses, protozoa and microalgae also synthesize these valuable pigments. Microbial production of carotenoids is gaining popularity due to its advantages over plant-based methods. These include shorter production times, controlled fermentation conditions, and the capacity to utilize inexpensive agro-industrial by-products as fermentation media, helping to cut down overall manufacturing costs. Carotenoids play critical roles not only as colorants but also as bioactive compounds with strong antioxidant properties. They help in neutralizing reactive oxygen species and safeguarding against oxidative stress-related diseases such as cancer, cardiovascular disorders and age-related muscular degeneration. This dual function as both colouring agents and

health promoting compounds makes them highly valuable in nutraceutical, pharmaceutical areas and cosmetic domains.[50]

3.1.2. Classification of Carotenoids

Carotenoids are generally grouped into two major types based on their chemical composition: [51]

Xanthophylls- Contain oxygen atoms in their structure. Examples include lutein, zeaxanthin, α -cryptoxanthin, and β -cryptoxanthin. Xanthophylls are especially important for eye health and have photoprotective properties.

Carotenes- Consist only of carbon and hydrogen atoms, lacking oxygen. Examples include β -carotene, lycopene, and toluene derivatives. Carotenes are key in protecting photosynthetic organisms from light-induced oxidative damage.

3.1.3. Biosynthesis of Carotenoids

Carotenoid biosynthesis begins with the reaction involving three isopentenyl pyrophosphate (IPP) entities and one dimethylallyl pyrophosphate (DMAPP) compounds to form geranylgeranyl pyrophosphate (GGPP), a C₂₀ intermediate that acts as the direct precursor for various carotenoids. The pathway continues through a series of desaturation, cyclization, and oxidation steps, varying by organism and carotenoid type.[52]

Fig 1. Biosynthesis pathway in microorganisms of Carotenoid (Di Salvo et al 2023)

3.1.4. Microbial Producers and Specialized Carotenoids

Several microbial species are capable of carotenoid biosynthesis, including bacteria such as *Pseudomonas putida*, *Dietzia natronolimnaea*, *Micrococcus roseus*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*; yeasts like *Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous*, *Yarrowia lipolytica*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Pichia pastoris*, *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa*, and *Sporidiobolus pararoseus*; fungi such as *Blakeslea trispora*; and algae including *Chlorella zofingiensis*, *Dunaliella salina*, and *Coelastrella striolata* [53]. Among the specialized carotenoids produced by these microbes, canthaxanthin is an orange-pink pigment synthesized by *Micrococcus roseus*, halophilic bacteria like *Haloferax alexandrinus*, and species such as *Bradyrhizobium* spp. and *Sphingomicrobium astaxanthinifaciens*; it exhibits potent antioxidant activity and is used in cosmetics as a skin tanning agent. Staphyloxanthin, a golden carotenoid produced by *Staphylococcus aureus*, serves as both an antioxidant and a virulence factor, contributing to the bacterium's resistance to host immune defences. Astaxanthin, a red-orange pigment produced by organisms like *Altererythrobacter ishigakiensis* and certain algae, is renowned

for its exceptional antioxidant properties and is widely utilized in nutraceuticals and aquaculture. Flexirubin, though not a typical carotenoid, is a structurally similar pigment with a phenyl-octanoic acid chromophore and resorcinol substituent, first discovered in *Chitinophaga filiformis* (formerly *Flexibacter elegans*), and serves as a distinctive pigment in certain gliding bacteria.[54]

3.2. Indigodines

Indigodines are natural blue pigments produced by several bacterial species through a biosynthetic pathway involving specialized non-ribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPSs). The synthesis of indigodine occurs via the formation of two molecules of L-form of glutamine, facilitated by NRPS enzymes encoded within specific biosynthetic gene clusters. These biosynthetic pathways enable the formation of structurally stable indigoid pigments under relatively simple fermentation conditions.[55]

A variety of bacterial genera have been identified as indigodine producers, including *Pseudomonas indigofera*, *Arthrobacter*, *Erwinia*, *Corynebacterium*, *Vogesella*, *Clavibacter*, *Photorhabdus*, *Phaeobacter*, *Dickeya*, and *Streptomyces*. These microbes naturally synthesize indigo pigments either as part of secondary metabolic activity or in response to environmental stressors. Indigodines possess significant biological and functional properties, which make them attractive for pharmaceutical and industrial applications. One of the primary roles of indigodine in microbial systems is its antioxidant activity, mitigating cellular damage resulting from free radicals. This free radical scavenger capability contributes to microbial survival in oxidative environments and may extend similar protective benefits when used in therapeutic applications[56] In addition to their antioxidant effects, indigodines exhibit antibacterial activity. For example, studies have shown that indigodine inhibits the growth of *Vibrio fischeri*, suggesting its potential as a natural antimicrobial agent in

controlling pathogenic bacteria. These properties highlight indigodine's viability as a bioactive compound. The multifunctional nature of indigodines extends beyond simple pigmentation. Reported bioactivities include: Antioxidant properties, Antibacterial effects, Functioning as intracellular signalling molecules, Participation in regulatory and metabolic cellular processes. Due to these attributes, indigodine and related microbial indigoid pigments are being explored as environmentally friendly substitutes for chemical dyes, particularly in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and biotechnological applications. Their natural origin, coupled with biological efficacy, positions indigodines as promising candidates for further industrial development.[57]

Fig2. Biosynthetic Pathway of Indigodine

3.3. Melanin

The pigment melanin is a photochemical stable, insoluble with a relatively high molar mass, produced by various eukaryotic microorganisms through enzymatic oxidation processes. Several bacterial genera, including *Rhizobium*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Klebsiella*, are known to synthesize distinct types of melanin pigments [58]. Melanin is broadly classified into two main types: eumelanin and pheomelanin. Eumelanin primarily contributes to the hues of hair ranging from black to brown, eyes, and skin in humans and other animals, and is biosynthesized via the oxidative polymerization of tyrosine derivatives.[59] Microbial production of melanin offers distinct benefits over conventional sources such as botanical,

zoological sources and synthetic manufacturing methods. Melanin pigments synthesized by microorganisms serve important photo protective functions by shielding cells and organisms from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation, preventing free radical formation, and scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS). Additionally, melanin exhibits versatile physicochemical properties, functioning as a UV absorber, cation exchanger, drug carrier, semiconductor, and X-ray absorber [60]. The photoprotective and antioxidant properties of melanin have garnered significant interest for biomedical applications, including use in sunscreens, wound healing, and radio protective agents. Microbial derived melanin has the added benefit of being adaptable to different environmental conditions and can be produced autonomously regardless of seasonal variations, offering a sustainable alternative to synthetic melanin polymers. Synthetic melanin, in contrast, often raise concerns related to quality control and environmental impact. Therefore, microbial melanin production represents a promising and eco-friendly approach to generating high-quality natural pigments with diverse industrial and pharmaceutical applications [61].

3.4. Prodigiosin

Prodigiosin is a red pigment primarily localized within intracellular and extracellular vesicles attached to the inner membrane of producing cells. It is predominantly synthesized by *Serratia marcescens* strains and other microorganisms including *Serratia nematodiphila*, *Serratia plymuthica*, *Serratia rubidaea*, *Pseudoalteromonas rubra*, *Vibrio* spp., *Janthinobacterium*, *Pseudomonas putida*, *Streptomyces coelicolor*, and *Hahella chejuensis* through microbial fermentation processes. Prodigiosin is a tripyrrole compound characterized by three distinct pyrrole rings: pyrrole (ring A), 3-methoxypyrrole (ring B), and 2-methyl-3-pentylpyrrole (ring C). Its molecular formula is $C_{27}H_{35}N_3O$ (15). The biosynthesis of prodigiosin involves the enzymatic condensation of two crucial precursors: 2-methyl-3-n-

amyl-pyrrole (MAP) and 4-methoxy-2,2'-bipyrrrole-5-carbaldehyde (MBC). This process follows a bifurcated three-step pathway that starts from 2-octenoyl CoA, with MBC specifically synthesized from L-proline. The entire pathway is regulated by the pig gene cluster, where transcription initiates upstream of pigA. Gene's pigB through pigE encode enzymes that drive MAP biosynthesis, while pigF to pigN are responsible for facilitating the final condensation of MAP and MBC to form prodigiosin [62]. Prodigiosin exhibits multiple bioactive properties, including significant cytotoxic effects against various cancer cell lines and multidrug-resistant strains, while showing minimal toxicity toward normal cells. It also demonstrates antimicrobial activity and electrical conductivity, making it a compound of interest for diverse applications [63] For industrial production, genetic improvement and strain selection for enhanced prodigiosin yield, along with efficient extraction methods, are critical. Challenges remain in purifying and separating prodigiosin at large scale to optimize production cost-effectiveness. Utilizing inexpensive agro-industrial wastes as substrates has proven effective in lowering production costs and enhancing yields. For instance, marine chitinous waste (MCW) serves as a promising carbon and nitrogen source for prodigiosin production by *Serratia marcescens*, offering a sustainable and economical fermentation strategy (pro). [64]

3.5. Violacein

Violacein is a naturally occurring purple pigment synthesized by various bacterial species, notably *Chromobacterium violaceu*, *Janthinobacterium lividum*, *Pseudoalteromonas* sp., along with other *Alteromonas luteoviolacea* [65]. Structurally, violacein is an indolocarbazole alkaloid derived from the condensation of two molecules of tryptophan, and it is closely related to the compound deoxyviolacein . The molecule comprises of three structural units: 5-hydroxyindole, oxindole, and 2-pyrrolidone [66] The biosynthesis of violacein initiates

initiated by VioA-catalyzed oxidation of L-tryptophan, a process mediated by a flavin-dependent tryptophan-2-monooxygenase, into 3-indole pyruvic acid imine (IPA imine). This intermediate is then dimerized by VioB, and subsequently, VioE converts it into protoviolaceinic acid (PVA). [67] Further enzymatic modifications by VioD, an NADP-dependent oxygenase, hydroxylate PVA to produce violaceinic acid. Finally, another NADP-dependent oxygenase adds a hydroxyl group to the C2 position of the other indole ring to form violacein [68] Violacein possesses a broad spectrum of bioactivities including antimicrobial, antiparasitic, and antitumor properties, which have spurred interest in its pharmaceutical and biotechnological applications [69]

3.6. Pyocyanin

Pyocyanin is a blue pigment predominantly produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with around 90–95% of strains capable of synthesizing this metabolite. Chemically, pyocyanin is a phenazine derivative composed of the subunit 1-hydroxy-2-methylphenazine. It contributes substantially to the virulence and persistence of *P. aeruginosa* by producing reactive oxygen species and interfering with host cellular processes. The biosynthesis of pyocyanin begins with tsmic acid through the shikimate pathway. The phenazine biosynthetic gene cluster (*phzA* to *phzG*) encodes enzymes that catalyze this conversion. PCA is then transformed into pyocyanin through methylation and hydroxylation reactions facilitated by the enzymes PhzM and PhzS, respectively. This results in the formation of the final compound, 1-hydroxy-5-methylphenazine, commonly known as pyocyanin. Pyocyanin's natural origin, biodegradability, and ease of production using low-cost substrates make it a valuable compound in biotechnology and biomedicine. Its rapid biosynthesis and straightforward extraction procedures support its potential applications in various industrial and medical fields. [70]

4. Application of Microbial Pigments

4.1. Employing Microbial Pigments for Therapeutic and Pharmaceutical Purpose

Microbial pigments have attracted increasing interest in the pharmaceutical and medical fields due to their diverse biological activities, encompassing antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, antiviral, and anticancer properties. These bioactivities are often facilitated through complex interactions with key cellular components such as membranes, proteins, and DNA. Owing to their natural origin, biocompatibility, and therapeutic potential, microbial pigments are emerging as valuable candidates for the development of safe, sustainable, and innovative medical therapies. Many microbial pigments exhibit antimicrobial activity by disrupting microbial membrane integrity, inhibiting protein synthesis, or interfering with essential metabolic processes. Some also act as anti-inflammatory agents by modulating specific signaling pathways involved in inflammation, helping to manage chronic and acute inflammatory conditions.[71]

One well-known pigment is violacein, a violet compound produced by bacteria such as *Chromobacterium violaceum*. Violacein demonstrates strong antimicrobial effects against Gram-positive bacteria, fungi, and parasitic organisms, including *Staphylococcus aureus*. Similarly, fucoxanthin, a brown xanthophyll pigment found in the chloroplasts of brown algae and heterokonts, shows broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, including effectiveness against multidrug-resistant pathogens like MRSA, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes*. [72] In the field of oncology, microbial pigments such as prodigiosin have shown significant potential. Prodigiosin, a red pigment synthesized by *Serratia marcescens* and other microorganisms, exhibits potent anticancer activity against several cancer types, including breast cancer, lung cancer, and melanoma. It induces apoptosis (programmed cell

death) in targets cancer cells while sparing normal cells, presenting a promising approach for targeted cancer therapies with fewer side effects than conventional treatments.[73]

Beyond their antimicrobial and anticancer applications, microbial pigments are being investigated for a broad spectrum of medical and therapeutic purposes. These include serving as natural antibiotic agents, components in topical treatments for skin infections, and ingredients in antiviral and antiseptic formulations. Additionally, they are being incorporated into wound-healing gels, anti-inflammatory preparations, and as cellular protective agents, highlighting their versatile potential in healthcare. Their versatility positions them as key tools in combating antibiotic resistance, managing chronic inflammation, and developing next-generation therapeutics. Additionally, microbial pigments contribute significantly to the nutraceutical and dietary supplement sectors. For example, riboflavin (vitamin B2) produced by both microorganisms and plants are an essential nutrient that serves as a precursor to the coenzymes FMN and FAD. These coenzymes are critical for energy metabolism, particularly in ATP production, and play a central role in cellular respiration, oxygen utilization, and normal cellular development. Another vital group of microbial pigments is carotenoids, which act both as antioxidants and precursors to vitamin A (retinol). Since humans cannot synthesize carotenoids, they must be obtained through diet or supplementation. Currently, most carotenoids available commercially are derived through chemical synthesis or plant extraction, but microbial fermentation offers a sustainable, cost-effective, and scalable alternative for large-scale production.[74]

Microbial pigments possess a broad spectrum of pharmacological properties and offer a natural, safe, and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic compounds in medical and pharmaceutical applications. Their roles in drug discovery, nutritional supplementation, and targeted therapies make them highly promising for future healthcare innovations. With on-

going advancements in biotechnology, metabolic engineering, and industrial fermentation, microbial pigment production is expected to expand significantly, unlocking new opportunities for medical and therapeutic use.[75]

4.2. Roles of Microbe-Derived Pigments in Food Products

Microbial pigments, owing to their natural origin, safety, and health-promoting properties, have emerged as a promising alternative to synthetic food colorants. Microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, and algae are capable of producing a wide variety of pigments, including carotenoids, flavins, melanins, quinones, monascins, and violacein. These pigments not only impart vivid, stable colors to food products but also function serving as food enhancers, natural antioxidants, coloring agents, and bioactive components in health-focused products. Significant microbially sourced pigments employed in food products include canthaxanthin, astaxanthin, beta-carotene, prodigiosin, violacein, riboflavin, phycocyanin, melanin, and lycopene. Beyond their aesthetic function, many of these compounds exhibit bioactivities including free-radical scavenging, tumor-inhibiting, pathogen-fighting, inflammation-reducing, and immune-modulating activities, enhancing the functional value of food products.[76]

Microbial fermentation offers several advantages over plant- or animal-based colorant sources, such as lower production costs, higher yields, simplified extraction, consistent quality, and year-round production. Additionally, advances in metabolic and genetic engineering enable strain improvements to enhance pigment yield, stability, and functionality. Importantly, many microbial pigments have been granted GRAS (Generally Recognized As Safe) status or are undergoing regulatory review, reinforcing their potential for safe incorporation into food products. Examples like phycocyanin from *Spirulina* are already in commercial use in dairy alternatives, beverages, and confectionery. Microbial

pigments align well with growing consumer demand for clean-label, sustainable, and health-conscious ingredients. While challenges such as pigment stability and regulatory approvals still exist, ongoing biotechnological innovations are addressing these issues. As a result, microbial fermentation is becoming an increasingly attractive and eco-friendly platform for producing high-quality, natural food colorants across a variety of applications.[77] Algae are increasingly being used as natural sources of food colorants. For example, phycocyanin, a vibrant blue pigment extracted from *Spirulina*, is commonly used to naturally color foods and beverages, including ice cream and other desserts. Another algal pigment, lutein, obtained from *Chlorella*, is a yellow compound with strong antioxidant properties and is easily incorporated into food products as a natural colorant. Additionally, phycoerythrin, derived from *Porphyridium cruentum* and other red microalgae, is currently being explored for use as a food dye due to its antioxidant, anticancer, and immunoregulatory activities, making it a functional ingredient with both coloring and health-promoting benefits.[78]

4.3. Cosmetic Applications of Microbial Pigments

Recent years have witnessed a notable surge in both the production and investigation of microbial pigments to meet the growing demand for natural and safe ingredients in the cosmetics industry. The frequent use of cosmetic products and sunscreens to protect the skin from environmental stressors particularly rising ultraviolet (UV) radiation levels has led to increased concerns about the safety of synthetic chemicals, which are often linked to adverse effects such as skin irritation, allergies, and long-term health risks.[79]

As a result, the cosmetics industry is increasingly turning to natural alternatives, including pigments derived from bacteria, fungi, and microalgae, to formulate safer and more effective products. These microbial pigments not only offer vibrant colors but also possess bioactive protection against UV-induced damage, along with strong antioxidant and anti-inflammatory

activities. Immune enhancement, and anti-aging benefits. Additionally, some pigments can inhibit melanogenesis, making them suitable for skin-lightening or brightening formulations. Key microbial pigments explored for cosmetic use include chlorophyll, β -carotene, lycopene, melanin, fucoxanthin, lycoxanthin, astaxanthin, xanthophylls, and phycobiliproteins. Their roles extend beyond coloring; they function as active ingredients in sunscreens, anti-aging creams, moisturizers, and serums due to their protective and restorative properties.[80] One of the most studied pigments is astaxanthin, primarily derived from *Haematococcus pluvialis* and marine yeast. Astaxanthin is considered one of the most powerful natural antioxidants, offering protection against UV-induced oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, and skin aging. It has been shown to improve skin texture, reduce wrinkles, and enhance moisture retention. Its superior antioxidant capacity higher unlike zeaxanthin, lutein, or β -carotene, this property is due to the presence of carbonyl groups in its ionone ring. Products like AstaBlanc by Kose (Japan) and AstaReal by AstaReal AB (Sweden) have successfully incorporated astaxanthin for anti-aging and skin-rejuvenating effects.[81]

Another promising pigment is lycopene, particularly from cyanobacteria such as *Anabaena vaginicola*, which contains higher concentrations than other known sources. Lycopene is widely used in anti-aging products due to its strong antioxidant properties. Similarly, β -cryptoxanthin, found in *Dunaliella salina* and other microalgae, has been reported to stimulate hyaluronic acid production, essential for maintaining skin hydration and elasticity[82].

Fucoxanthin, extracted from *Laminaria japonica*, has shown the ability to inhibit tyrosinase activity key enzyme in melanin production and suppress melanogenesis at the transcriptional level, making it a valuable agent in products targeting hyperpigmentation and uneven skin tone. Furthermore, pigments such as phycoerythrin and phycoerythrobilins, derived from

Spirulina (Cyanobacteria) and Porphyridium (Rhodophyta), are being utilized as natural colorants in lipsticks, eyeliners, and creams. Some microbial-derived colorless carotenoids (CLCs) have also been incorporated into cosmeceuticals. Despite lacking color, CLCs offer antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and UV-protective effects, and are commonly found in moisturizers, sunscreens, and as enhancers in CoQ10-based formulations. These compounds help protect the skin from oxidative damage and prevent collagen degradation, thereby slowing the aging process.[83]

Historically, cosmetic products have relied heavily on synthetic pigments, including metal-based colorants such as cadmium and chromium, which are now recognized as toxic and potentially carcinogenic. Early cosmetic formulations failed to account for these risks, leading to severe health consequences such as deformities, blindness, and even death. While regulations have improved, increasing health-conscious consumers are fueling the demand for clean-label, natural cosmetic products and are prepared to pay higher prices for options that promise both safety and efficacy. Despite some limitations such as challenges in pigment extraction, formulation stability, and regulatory approval on-going research continues to explore new microbial strains, novel pigments, sustainable extraction methods, and expanded applications. For example, recent studies suggest that marine-derived compounds may provide safer and more effective tyrosinase inhibitors; with some already replacing banned synthetic compounds like hydroquinone in Europe.[84] With forecasts indicating the natural cosmetics market will grow to USD 54.5 billion worldwide by 2027, there is an urgent need to scale up the production of bioactive pigments beyond the currently available options such as astaxanthin, monascins, and β -carotene. As such, microbial pigments represent a sustainable, multifunctional, and consumer-preferred alternative for the next generation of cosmetics and skincare products.[85]

4.4. Microbial-Based Dyes for Textile Applications

Microbial pigments are emerging as sustainable and environmentally sustainable substitutes for chemical dyes used in textiles. Unlike traditional chemical dyes, which involve toxic reagents and produce hazardous waste, microbial pigments are naturally derived from bacteria, fungi, and microalgae, and can be produced through scalable fermentation processes. These bio-based dyes offer vibrant, long-lasting colors along with functional benefits including pathogen-inhibiting, free-radical neutralizing, and inflammation-reducing properties, adding value beyond aesthetics. Prodigiosin, a striking red pigment produced by *Vibrio spp.* and *Serratia marcescens*, has notably been used to dye various fabrics like wool, nylon, acrylic, rayon, satin, and silk, with excellent colorfastness even after repeated washing and rubbing. Similarly, **violacein**, a violet pigment from *Chromobacterium violaceum* and *Janthinobacterium lividum*, imparts deep blue tones to silk and cotton. These bacteria can also co-produce proteases, which enhance fiber softness and improve dye uptake during processing. *Chromobacterium violaceum* has further demonstrated successful application on cotton, satin, and polyester, while prodigiosin-treated rayon and satin maintained vibrant hues under physical stress.[86]

Fungi also contribute to microbial dye development. *Fusarium oxysporum* has been used to dye wool, while *Talaromyces verruculosus* produces a safe, non-cytotoxic red pigment suitable for cotton. A yellow pigment from *Thermomyces* species has shown high dye affinity for silk, outperforming other natural fabrics in color retention. One of the most significant advantages of microbial pigments is their tunability. Through optimization of culture conditions or genetic engineering, pigment yield and functionality can be enhanced. For example, Alihoseini et al. demonstrated that mutant strains of *Vibrio gazogenes* could be engineered to produce dyes with strongly effect the microbial growth, particularly targeting *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and imparting additional hygienic properties to textiles. Another key benefit is biodegradability. During dyeing, any pigment runoff into

water systems poses minimal risk, as these natural pigments can be broken down by microbial life, unlike persistent synthetic dyes. The presence of bioactive compounds also makes these dyes safe for human use, aquatic ecosystems, and animals. As consumer demand shifts toward sustainable, non-toxic, and ethically sourced products, microbial dyes are increasingly seen as the future of green textile manufacturing. Their low environmental footprint, biological functionality, and compatibility with fermentation-based mass production make them ideal for transforming the textile industry into a more sustainable and responsible sector.[87]

4.5. Environmental and Commercial Uses of Microbial Pigments

Microbial pigments are now seen as eco-friendly, multipurpose alternatives to synthetic dyes and chemicals, offering wide-ranging applications across industrial and environmental sectors. Their sustainable production, cost-effectiveness, and diverse color profiles make them valuable in textile dyeing, agriculture, nanotechnology, aquaculture, and biosensing. In textile industries, pigments like violacein and pyocyanin not only provide vibrant coloration but also impart antimicrobial and antioxidant benefits to fabrics. In agriculture, pigments such as prodigiosin from *Serratia marcescens* and violacein from *Chromobacterium violaceum* act as effective biopesticides against pests and pathogens, including *Drosophila* larvae, ants, and termites, and hold therapeutic potential against diseases like Chagas. Nanotechnology has embraced microbial pigments such as actinorhodin, melanin, flexirubin, phycocyanin, phycoerythrin, and bacterioruberin for biosynthesizing nanoparticles with enhanced antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticancer properties. Marine-derived pigments like glaukothalin from *Rheinheimera* sp. and pyocyanin from *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* demonstrate potent antibacterial activity and show promise in textile dyeing and plant pathogen control. Environmentally, pigments function as biosensors (e.g., violacein for lead

detection) and antifoulants; prodigiosin, for example, inhibits the growth of marine fouling organisms such as *Gallionella* and *Alteromonas* and reduces cyanobacterial adhesion, providing a sustainable alternative to toxic antifouling agents. Pigments from *Micrococcus* species also exhibit wound-healing and anti-inflammatory effects, while bacterioruberin carotenoids from halophilic bacteria display strong antioxidant and antibacterial activity. In aquaculture and animal husbandry, dietary carotenoids like astaxanthin, zeaxanthin, lutein, and β -carotene improve larval survival, egg production, growth, and stress resilience, and may enhance phototactic behaviour in fish larvae. Functional pigments like phycobiliproteins and chlorophyll derivatives further boost feed quality and animal health. Additionally, to minimize environmental impact during pigment recovery, green extraction techniques including ultrasound, microwave, enzyme, ionic liquid, and pressurized liquid-assisted methods have replaced traditional solvent-based processes. Overall, microbial pigments represent a promising class of bioresources driving innovation in sustainable biotechnology, with continued research into their ecological roles, genomic pathways, and industrial scalability poised to expand their applications even further.[88]

Fig.3 Possible applications of Pigments.

5. Conclusion

Microbial pigments represent a vibrant and sustainable frontier in biotechnology. Their natural origin, eco-friendly production, and multifunctional properties make them ideal for applications spanning textiles, agriculture, medicine, aquaculture, and environmental protection. With advancements in microbial engineering, fermentation optimization, and green extraction technologies, microbial pigments are positioned to replace synthetic dyes and toxic chemicals in many industries. Future research focused on uncovering novel pigment-producing strains, elucidating biosynthetic pathways, and scaling up production will be critical in unlocking the full potential of these biological colorants. As the world shifts toward sustainable practices, microbial pigments offer a compelling solution for cleaner, greener industrial processes.

6.Data Availability:

No dataset was used or created during the study.

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